

Deliverable 1.3

Data management plan

Version 2

WP 1
Deliverable 1.3
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Executive summary

During the project, the consortium will generate an extensive amount of data. All the resulting data, necessary to replicate the study's findings, will be publicly available without restriction at the time of publication and stated in the required journal's Data Availability Statement. When specific legal or ethical restrictions prohibit public sharing of a data set, authors will indicate how others may obtain access to the data. In particular, data generated by next-generation sequencing (NGS) have to be properly managed to be readable and usable for future research and researchers. In this way, data management will be done according to FAIR principles, particularly: In each task of the scientific project several organisms will be sequenced to study and comprehend the response against viruses and pathogens of the cultured fish once fed with two levels of amino-acid supplemented diets. All sequencing data will be uploaded into the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) BioProject platform (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/>) and assigned a permanent BioProject ID for identification, linked to metadata to allow full interpretation of the data. This will provide open access to the information both using web browsers and bioinformatics queries, complying with the Findable and Accessible information strategy. Also, all data generated will have an accession number that will interlink several databases such as Genbank, InterPro or PubMed. The shared vocabularies and ontologies are in concordance with the Interoperable and Reusable use of the information. All the raw data generated will be put at the disposition of the scientific community as soon as generated, and then linked to open-access publications.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
DEB	Dissemination and Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
SC	Steering Committee
TL	Task Leaders
TMC	Technical Management Committee
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders

1. Introduction

The primary components of the data management strategy for the data that will be gathered, processed, or generated in the context of the project are described in the data management plan (DMP). The FAIR principles (data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) guided the development of the DMP. It's a live document that will be updated throughout the project with partners' input whenever important changes occur.

2. Data summary

The welfare of farmed animals is a subject of increasing societal concern within Europe, a fact that underpins the present application to support research into the improvement of animal health and welfare. IGNITION is a structured attempt to gather new knowledge on animals' resilience to environmental challenges while discovering new non-invasive health and welfare biomarkers. In WP2 experiments will be performed to gain deeper insight into farmed animal welfare under a climate change scenario considering current farming practices. These efforts will be directed at the effects of acute (handling and transport) and chronic stress (heat waves). It will study nutritional strategies for improving fish welfare and health when facing these stressful events. WP3 will develop optimal extraction of biocompounds from halophytes to test their pro- and pre-biotic activity in fish and shrimp diets in terms of fish performance, gut health and disease resistance. WP4 will focus on the development of vaccination strategies against tenacibaculosis and infectious salmonid anaemia. It also aims to develop and optimise the Outer Membrane Vesicle (OMV) basis for loading viral and bacterial antigens. Different OMV vaccination methodologies will be assessed. Data from WP2, 3 and 4 will feed into WP5, which aims to discover and select biomarkers which might be suitable to be integrated into sensor devices that may monitor health and detect disease in farmed animals. With this, the next step will be to develop non-invasive sensors for quantitative analysis of selected biomarkers in farm products and to validate these protocols. In WP6, the genetic component of stress response studied in the previous WP will be characterized and correlations between broad-scale phenotypes and molecular responses will be searched to test the potential for incorporation of novel phenotypes into breeding programs. WP7 will ensure that the knowledge developed under IGNITION reaches its stakeholders and that they are aware of the potential utilization and impact of the project outputs. WP1 will deal with all official administrative documentation. Further details of the WPs and tasks therein can be found in Table 1, and an overview of the research data can be found in Table 2.

Table 1: List of WPs and tasks in IGNITION

WP	Task
1 Coordination and project management	1.1 Establishment of all operational bodies in the IGNITION consortium
	1.2 Strategic management
	1.3 Technology and risk management
	1.4 Coordination and project execution
	1.5 Project Manual
	1.6 Organization of kick-off and periodic meetings
	1.7 Ethical principles
	1.8 Data management plan
2 Animal welfare in a changing environment	2.1 Studies related to acute stress responses in fish
	2.2 Studies related to chronic stress responses
	2.3 Nutritional strategies to improve fish resilience to stress
	2.4 Development of OWIs for shrimp
	2.5 Estimating genetic parameters for disease resistance and climate change resilience in the Manila clam
	2.6 Field validation of biomarkers, biosensors, and functional diets
	2.7 Analysis of sediment and water column microbiome for pathogen detection
	2.8 Business Plan and bio-economic modelling
3 Halophytes biorefinery and functional feeds	3.1 Extraction of bioactives
	3.2 Probiotic fermentation of green biomass
	3.3 In vitro trials for bioactives screening
	3.4 Feed formulation and feeding trials with fish and shrimp
	3.5 Challenge tests
	3.6 Microbiome analysis
4 Animal immunisation approaches	4.1 <i>Tenacibaculum maritimum</i> vaccination protocol and efficiency evaluation
	4.2 ISAV vaccine strategy
	4.3 Vaccine potency and efficacy and safety
	4.4 Uptake of vaccine antigens via bath: Retention and expression of immune genes
	4.5 OMV-based platform for development of multivalent fish vaccines
	4.6 Synergistic effects of functional feeds and vaccination
5 Non-invasive tools and machine learning	5.1 Machine learning/disease prediction tools
	5.2 Innovative generation of antibodies to fish proteins
	5.3 Integration of biomarkers into innovative sensor technology for non-invasive on farm tools
	5.4 Field trial for biomarkers and biosensors verification
6 Genomic tools and molecular phenotyping to improve animal welfare	6.1 Genetic component of the ACUTE stress response in fish and genetic correlation to biomarkers
	6.2 Genetic component of the CHRONIC stress response in fish and genetic correlation to biomarkers
	6.3 Assess the genetic component of response to prophylactics and pathogen challenges
	6.4 Manila clam genotyping

		6.5	Genetic component of immune response in seabass
7	Dissemination, exploitation and communication	7.1	Communication and dissemination activities, tools, materials and channels
		7.2	Innovation management, exploitation, and sustainability
		7.3	Stakeholder uptake
		7.4	Cooperation with EC services and coordination and clustering with relevant networks, initiatives, and projects
		7.5	Policy outreach and recommendations

Table 2. Management of research data in IGNITION

<u>Task</u>	<u>Origin of data</u>	<u>Raw data form</u>	<u>Summary of results</u>	<u>Storage type</u>	<u>Data integration and reuse</u>	<u>Dissemination level</u>	<u>Partners involved</u>	
1.1 to 1.8	No data compiled							
2.1	Clinical evaluation	xlsx	Validation studies	Local / GDrive	WP5 & 6	Confidential until IP rights have been safeguarded	CIIMAR, RIA, UCA	
2.2							CIIMAR, RIA, UCA, GIFAS	
2.3							CIIMAR, UCA, RIA, Visifish, SWU	
2.4					Welfare evaluation Microbiome analysis		WP5	SWU, Visifish
2.5					Clinical evaluation		WP5 & 6	CIIMAR, UNIPD, UEDIN
2.6					Welfare evaluation		WP3 & 5 WP5	GIFAS
2.7					Microbiome analysis			GIFAS, CIIMAR, NORD
2.8	No data compiled							
3.1	Extraction of different compounds	xlsx	Optimization studies	Local	WP3	Confidential until IP rights have been safeguarded	AAU	
3.2	Chemical analysis				WP3		AAU, Halorefine	
3.3	Clinical evaluation		Validation studies	Local / GDrive	WP5		AAU, Halorefine, CIIMAR, NORD	

3.4	Biomass composition and clinical analysis				WP3, 4 & 5		CIIMAR, RIA, Sparos
3.5	Clinical evaluation				WP3, 4, 5 & 6		CIIMAR, RIA
3.6	Microbiome analysis				WP5 & 6		NORD
4.1	Clinical evaluation	xlsx	Validation studies	Local / GDrive	WP4 & 5	Confidential until IP rights have been safeguarded	UiT
4.2							I3S
4.3					CIIMAR; I3S, UiT, RIA		
4.4							
4.5							
4.6					WP5 & 6		
5.1	Data modelling		Machine learning	Local	WP5	Confidential until IP rights have been safeguarded	SPAROS, CIIMAR; RIA, UCA, UNIPD, UiT, NORD, I3S
5.2	Clinical evaluation	xlsx	Validation studies	Local / GDrive			CIIMAR
5.3	Technology development						UCC
5.4	Clinical evaluation	xlsx	Validation studies	Local / GDrive			CIIMAR, UCC, GIFAS, SPAROS
6.1	Clinical evaluation	Xlsx			WP6	Confidential until IP rights have been safeguarded	UEDIN, CIIMAR, RIA, UCA
6.2							UEDIN, CIIMAR; UCA, RIA, GIFAS
6.3							UEDIN, CIIMAR, RIA
6.4		genotyping					
6.5	No data produced						
7.1 to 7.5	questionnaires	xlsx	doc	Local / GDrive		Confidential	All partners

3. FAIR principles

3.1. Making data interoperable

3.1.1. Data storage and archive

Following principles of good practices, the official administrative data (i.e. consortium agreement, reports, deliverables, minutes, meeting presentations, publications, publication permissions, etc.) will be stored in the common Google Drive, where all the partners have access to the data. Each partner's facilities will keep raw data locally, following their internal regulations. Datasets will be processed and analysed using relevant characterization and analysis software. The creation of variable and quantity names will adhere to general data processing rules. Used abbreviations, technical terms and standards will be defined or mentioned in the document. Each partner will convert aggregated data into forms that are compatible with software that is frequently utilized.

Once ready and checked, each partner will upload a summary of the dataset in the Google Drive folder dedicated to data management. The summary will present the results (graphically or in a table format), accessible to all partners with commonly used software.

3.1.2. Sample labelling

A common sample labelling system has been agreed upon by all partners in the project. Each experiment will be registered on a Google form with all the relevant information (Figure 1). The Google form will allow editing the responses so that partners can correct the information if necessary. The resulting Excel file, with all common data about the experiment, will be accessible to the whole consortium but will not be editable, to avoid accidental loss of information. Codes for the samples will follow those described in Tables 3 to 6.

Table 3. Biomass species codes used in sample labelling

<u>Biomass source</u>	<u>Code</u>
<i>Salicornia ramosissima</i>	Sal
<i>Sueda maritima</i>	Sue

Table 4: Species codes used in sample labelling

<u>Species</u>	<u>Code</u>
European seabass	ES
Rainbow trout	RT

Atlantic salmon	AS
Whiteleg shrimp	WS
Manila clam	MC

Table 5: Sample code to be used in sample labelling

<u>Sample type</u>	<u>Code</u>
blood	bld
brain	bra
epiphytes (polychaetes / molluscs / sponges / tunicates)	epi
gills	gil
head-kidney	hk
hypophysis	hyp
intestine	gut
liver	liv
mucosal tissue	muc
plasma	pla
skin	skn
skin mucus	smu
sediment	mud
water column	h2o

Table 6: Analysis code used in sample labelling

<u>Sample analysis</u>	<u>Code</u>
cellular	cel
cortisol	cor
flesh quality	fls
genotype	gen
haematology	hem
humoral	hum
metabolism	msm
metabolites	mte
microbiome	bio

oxidative stress	oxi
proteome	pro
transcriptome	tra

The sample code will always follow the same structure:

IG (to identify the IGNITION project) <Task number> <species> <number of the experiment>
| <sample type> < analysis> | <institution where samples will be sent>

As an example, a first experiment in task 3.1, working with Atlantic salmon, where plasma is to be collected for humoral analysis, and the sample will be sent (or stay at) CIIMAR, will have the following tag: “GA 3.1 as 1 | pla hum | CIIMAR”. The sample form (Figure 1) includes information about the source of the samples but also their destination. Several sample types and analyses can be filled in for each experiment.

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IGNITION Sample registration

Because IGNITION is a strongly collaborative work, all experiments done in the context of the project should be registered and their samples should have standardized tags. Please fill in this form and use the tag according to the formula:

IG_Task_Species_number of the experiment | Sample type_Analysis | institution where samples will be sent

(ex. Task 2.1, European seabass, 1st experiment, Plasma, humoral, CIIMAR)
tag: IG_2.1_ES_1 | pla_hum | CIIMAR

You will receive on your email a copy of your response, and later an email with the tag that should be used

Figure 1. Form to register the experiment before its start so that standardized experiment sample codes can be generated.

The resulting Excel file will have information according to Table 7:

Table 7: structure of the sample registration form

	<u>Form questions</u>
Filled once for each experiment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name of the researcher • E-mail • Alternative contact name (optional) • Alternative contact email (optional) • Institution • Task number • Experiment number • Title of the experiment • Date of beginning of the experiment • Species • What is being tested
As many entries as necessary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample type • Sample analysis • Institution where samples will be sent

A second form will be used to gather more detailed information about each experiment (Figure 2), which will automatically fill the WP5 database with the background information on the datasets that result from the trials. It will also produce a detailed protocol, which can later be made available once the dataset is made publicly available.

Section 1 of 6

IGNITION protocol registration

Please fill in all details about your experiment methodology. The information asked here is essential for the implementation of WP5. Please make sure you complete this step.

THIS FORM IS EDITABLE.
The form is long, but simple, and you can complete the information later, or even change it if needed.

It also automatically create a protocol document (under '6. data management' > 'protocols') which can be used when publishing the dataset

Figure 2. Form to register the protocol and all the details that are needed both to create a protocol document and to implement WP5.

The WP5 database with details on the data will be available to everyone under 'IGNITION – Project-wide' > 'WP5 – non-invasive tools and machine learning' > 'Experimental data info.xlsx'. It will however be editable solely by the WP5 team.

The automatically generated protocols will be available to the whole consortium in the common Google Drive folder, under 'IGNITION – Project-wide' > '6. Data management' > 'Protocols'.

3.2. Data stewardship

Each institution nominated a data steward who will be the contact point between their institution and WP5, to make sure all data produced under IGNITION will be available to support the implementation of WP5 and that the data sets are up to date and all details available. This stewardship will also guarantee that all information is well organized and that doubts about any details of how the data was produced can be easily clarified.

3.3. Making data openly accessible

3.3.1. Data sharing, ownership and security

The consortium members will use the data throughout the project. All requests for additional data use after the project is finished will be carefully evaluated and, whenever possible, accepted by the partner(s) responsible for generating them. If there are no IPR or confidentiality concerns, or if there is no direct overlap between the study questions and the

primary research, permission for data use will be granted. The partner(s) responsible for generating the data will be the rightful owner(s) of the datasets. Securing and backing up the data will be the responsibility of the partners who generated it.

All sequencing data will be uploaded into the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) BioProject platform (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/>) and assigned a permanent BioProject ID for identification, linked to metadata to allow full interpretation of the data. This will provide open access to the information both using web browsers and bioinformatics queries, complying with the Findable and Accessible information strategy. All data generated will have an accession number that will interlink several.

To have reproducible results for future experiments in the area of nutrition supplementation and host-parasite interactions, the IGNITION consortium will provide all used scripts in open code hosting platforms such as GitHub. In this way, R or Python scripts for data analysis will be freely available to the community to increase transparency and prevent questionable research practices. In this sense, the authors will release all raw results collected during the research project to allow the full scrutiny of the results and contribute to the review and improvement of the scientific process.

Workshops and webinar events will be recorded and made available on the website of the project and on YouTube (an account will be created once resources are available for publishing) and disseminated on social media. In this way, IGNITION will provide advanced training in an open environment and freely available for all scientific, student and citizen communities interested in the topics discussed in the project.

3.3.2. Publication policy

The IGNITION project deliverables include both public and confidential documents. Project deliverables and other internal documents are frequently in the form of confidential reports, while paper publications are open to the public and will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. The project website, workshops, position paper and other communication materials will all serve as additional platforms for sharing project updates and knowledge gained during the project.

The dissemination and communication plan lists various channels through which the public papers and project information will be shared. Whenever feasible, the project coordinator (PC) will collaborate with the technology management committee (TMC) to take all necessary steps to make the data freely accessible and usable for third parties for research, teaching, and study purposes through licensing or other ways.

All peer-reviewed scientific articles will be freely available. Prior notice of any planned publication and patent application shall be given to the other Parties at least 15 calendar days

before the publication, as described in the GA and D1.1 – project management and communication portal

3.3.3. IPR management

The CA contains a description of fundamental IPR ideas, which can be summarized as:

- Results are owned by the Party that generates them
- The background IP owned by the partners before the commencement of the project is respected, and it is only non-exclusively bound to the project
- When necessary, patent applications will be submitted and approved for publication following section 3.2.2.

Exploitation and IP issues will be managed by the PC and PCC.

More information on IPR rules can be found in the GA article 16 and its annex 5 and in the CA article 8.

3.4. Making data interoperable

The standard data files will be prepared in Excel or Google Sheets. The units used will follow the rules in Table 6, as agreed by all partners.

Table 6: Standard data parameters

<u>Parameter</u>	<u>Unit</u>
Length	m (metric system)
Weight	g (gram)
Temperature	°C
Language	English (UK)
Decimal characters	. (point)

3.5. Making data reusable

Most of the information produced by IGNITION will be freely available under a Creative Commons license. Each dataset's metadata will provide the type of license and usage restrictions. One of the following is highly preferred:

- CC-O – Public Domain Dedication

By relinquishing all of his or her rights to the work under copyright laws everywhere, including any associated and adjacent rights, to the fullest extent permitted by law, you donated the work to the public domain.

Without seeking permission, everyone is free to copy, edit, distribute, and perform the work, even for profit.

More information on Universal Public Domain Dedication:
<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

- CC-BY – Attribution

Anyone using your work must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

For more information on Attribution 4.0 international:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

After the project's completion, open-access data produced by IGNITION will continue to be available for reuse. There are no plans to stop providing this data. As a result, it will be used once the protocols have been established or the research has been finished and published, as well as for as long as the archives last. After disclosure, access rights will rely on the Creative Commons license that those data or goods are covered by, as stated earlier in this section. The partner using the limited datasets must arrange any necessary negotiations with the data owners for the re-use of those datasets and/or products for the products generated using restricted data.

The data provider is primarily responsible for the initial quality control of the data during data collection. Any techniques or procedures for quality control can be described in the dataset's metadata. Datasets may need to undergo several quality control steps to be made available through international repositories. These steps are designed to increase the accuracy and completeness of the data.

4. Allocation of resources

The PC is responsible for data management in the project. Costs related to open-access publishing are included in partners' budgets.

5. Data security

To ensure that data FAIR principles are followed and to ensure that data related to IGNITION can be easily found, a common repository will be selected during the annual meeting. Zenodo and other certified platforms such as Re3Data and FAIRsharing will be considered.

6. Ethics and GDPR

All participants in this project have vowed to act responsibly and follow the laws and regulations in effect in the nations where the research will be conducted. No matter whose nation conducts the research, Horizon Europe's ethical standards and procedures will be strictly followed. The project complies with the European Union's Charter of Fundamental Rights.

The scientific disciplines covered by this proposal fall under the general research ethics, and they will be upheld. The project will adhere to Directive 2002/58/EC4 on privacy and electronic communications and Directive 1995/46/EC3 on the protection of persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

IGNITION shall adhere to Directive 2016/679 and the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) when collecting personal information for purposes such as workshop registration, survey responses, or newsletter subscriptions.

All consortium participants in this project will take ethical considerations into account, and the PC will monitor them. Any significant issues or deviations on the gender aspects will be reported to the Steering Committee.

Document information

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